

Notes

Polarographic Study of Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with Ethylene-1, 2-Bisdiphenylphosphineoxide

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ETHYLENE-1,2-bisdiphenylphosphineoxide (EDPO) has been found to form complexes with a number of metal ions, which have been characterised with the help of ir spectra, magnetic susceptibility and reflectance spectral data^{1,2}. The present work describes the polarographic investigations of the complexes of EDPO formed with Co²⁺ and Ni²⁺ ions in the presence of pyridine-potassium chloride buffer.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of B. D. H. Analar quality. Cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate (0.1 M) and nickel(II) chloride hexahydrate (0.1 M) solutions were prepared by standardising the stock solutions with standard EDTA. A buffer containing 0.05 M pyridine and 1.0 M potassium chloride was prepared by dissolving requisite amounts in doubly distilled water. A solution of ethylene-1,2-bisdiphenylphosphineoxide (0.01 M) was prepared in absolute alcohol (Bengal Chemicals). It was verified that ethanolic solution of ligand and the metal salt yielded a soluble complex. The complexes thus formed can also be separated by refluxing and concentrating the solution.

Automatic recording polarograph LP7 was used to record the polarograms. The polarizing speed was kept 20 mv/min. The accuracy of measurement was ± 1 mv. Measurements were made with Hume and Harris saturated calomel electrode as a reference electrode³. The cell was maintained at $30.0 \pm 0.01^\circ$. The characteristics of capillary used were $m = 3.3891$ mg./sec., $t = 2.740$ sec., $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.6690$ mg^{2/3}sec.^{-1/6}. Measurements were made with the mercury column 36.5 cm. high. Oxygen was removed from all solutions with pure nitrogen.

Results and Discussion

Polarographic investigations were carried out in buffer (0.05 M Py + 1.0 M KCl). Cobalt(II) and nickel(II) gave the reversible two electron reduction waves at dropping mercury electrode with half wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) -1.100 volts and -0.835 volts respectively. On adding increasing concentration of EDPO, it was observed that the wave shifted to more negative potentials. The observations are listed in tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAMS OF 10^{-2} M COBALT(II) IN THE PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF 10^{-2} M EDPO, $t = 30.0^\circ$

log [EDPO]	$E_{1/2}$ vs S. C. E., volts.
0.0000	-1.100
-3.8890	-1.112
-3.7500	-1.123
-3.6100	-1.135
-3.4700	-1.148

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAMS OF 10^{-2} M NICKEL (II) IN THE PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF 10^{-2} M EDPO; $t = 30.0^\circ$

log [EDPO]	$E_{1/2}$ vs S. C. E., volts
-0.0000	-0.835
-3.8889	-0.848
-3.7500	-0.857
-3.6000	-0.865
-3.4500	-0.875

The plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs log [EDPO] gave straight lines with slopes -0.098 for cobalt(II) and -0.044 for nickel (II). Applying the equation⁴

$$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{d \log [EDPO]} = \frac{-0.059}{n} (p - q)$$

(where n is the number of electrons involved in the reduction, and p and q are the number of ligand groups attached to the oxidised and reduced form respectively), we can determine the number of ligand groups attached to cobalt and nickel. As mentioned earlier $E_{1/2}$ against log [EDPO] gave slopes of -0.098 volts and -0.044 volts for cobalt(II) and nickel (II) respectively. Hence p (the number of ligand groups attached to the oxidised form) comes out to be $3.316 \approx 3.0$ for cobalt (II) and $2.034 \approx 2$ for nickel (II), where $q = 0$ and $n = 2$ in the equation given above. The electrode reactions, therefore may be expressed as

The order of formation constants was obtained by observing the shift of $E_{1/2}$ in function of the concentration of the ligand. The following equation may be applied⁵

$$(E_{1/2})_c - (E_{1/2})_s = \frac{0.059}{n} \log Kc - p \frac{0.059}{n} \log C_x$$

where $(E_{1/2})_c$ and $(E_{1/2})_s$ are the half wave potentials of the complex ion and the simple metal ions respectively, and C_x is the concentration of the ligand. The dissociation constants (Kc) of the complex ions calculated from the above equation for cobalt(II) and nickel(II) are 9.15×10^{-13} and 5.83×10^{-9} respectively. These values of dissociation constants indicate that Co^{2+} forms more stable complexes with EDPO than Ni^{2+} which is not in agreement with Irving-Williams order⁶. This may be attributed to the additional stabilization due to Jahn Teller effect present in cobalt(II). Thus polarographic study of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes with EDPO, reveals the formation of 1:3 and 1:2 complexes respectively.

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Phenyl Acetate Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), and Zn(II) with Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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THOUGH a lot of work has been done on halogeno substituted acetates¹⁻⁵ of first transition series metal ions, little has been done by varying the R-group of the carboxylates. Only recently Thornton⁶ and coworkers have reported some Ni(II) complexes of benzoates and substituted benzoates with heterocyclic amines. We have been studying the complexation of some divalent metal ion carboxylates⁷ with nitrogen ligand and reported earlier complexes of trichloroacetates⁸. This communication reports the studies on Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) phenyl acetates with some nitrogen ligands like quinoline, isoquinoline and 3-methyl pyridine.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Phenyl acetates of different metals were dissolved in absolute ethanol, treated with the nitrogen ligands in (1:2) proportion and the solution refluxed for thirty minutes over water bath. On cooling overnight compounds separated out. These were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

Physical measurements were made as described in an earlier communication⁹. Analytical data are recorded in Table-1 and spectral data in Table-2.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour and form	Conductance (mhos. cm ²)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	% Metal		% Nitrogen	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	R.qd.
NiL ₂ Q ₂	Green crystalline	8.5	2.9	9.95	10.07	4.45	4.77
NiL ₂ (I.Q) ₂	-do-	9.2	2.98	9.83	10.07	4.52	4.77
NiL ₂ (β -pic) ₂	-do-	8.1	3.15	11.14	11.40	5.28	5.44
CoL ₂ Q ₂	Pink crystalline	9.5	4.84	9.86	10.03	4.53	4.77
CoL ₂ (I.Q) ₂	-do-	8.8	4.96	9.91	10.03	4.55	4.77
CoL ₂ (β -pic) ₂	-do-	10.2	5.1	11.22	11.45	5.26	5.44
CuL ₂ Q ₂	Green crystalline	11.5	1.75	10.56	10.74	4.48	4.73
CuL ₂ (I.Q) ₂	-do-	11.8	1.83	11.62	10.74	4.54	4.73
CuL ₂ (β -pic) ₂	-do-	12.6	1.88	12.01	12.28	5.26	5.39
ZnL ₂ Q ₂	White crystalline	10.5	—	10.92	11.02	4.51	4.72
ZnL ₂ (I.Q) ₂	-do-	13.8	—	10.86	11.02	4.60	4.72
ZnL ₂ (β -pic) ₂	-do-	14.7	—	12.25	12.54	5.22	5.37

Q=quinoline; I.Q.=isoquinoline; β -pic=3-methyl pyridine